

EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS THROUGH LEGO FOR ENHANCING CRITICAL THINKING SKILL IN SCIENCE

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ABSTRACT: This paper considers the experiences of teaching through learning packages developed by using LEGO Mindstorms EV3. The tasks included the different activities with robotic kits provided to the students in order to know the effectiveness of educational robotics on critical thinking skills in science. The research was carried out over 14 weeks period of time in elementary schools situated in Pune city of India. Two intact classes were taken for the study. The design of the study was quasi-experimental wherein group was exposed to the robotics intervention while the other group, the control and was taught using conventional teaching method. The present study analysed posttest scores of students in the experimental group with students in a control group using analysis of covariance. After quantitative analysis of the findings, it was concluded that students in the experimental group with robotics intervention had a significant increase in mean scores on critical thinking in the posttest than the control group.

KEYWORDS: Educational robotics, Critical thinking, LEGO, Science

I. INTRODUCTION

Educational robotics has been used in the classroom for over a decade as an extracurricular activity but not as a regular subject. It is also not in usage as an aid to teaching in science classes in India yet. Keeping in mind all these things, the present research was carried out for fourteen weeks period in a school in India to study the effectiveness of the learning materials developed using Educational Robotics (Edu-Robotics) on critical thinking skills of elementary school students in science. LEGO Mindstorms EV3 Home edition (31313) robotic kits were used in developing learning materials for transacting science concepts based on the curricular contents of grade sixth science following NCERT (National Council of Educational Research and Training) curriculum. LEGO Mindstorms EV3 is the third-generation robotics kit in LEGO's Mindstorms line. It is a combination of two Danish words "leg godt" meaning "play well". It is an easy to learn robotics platform that provides young students a hands-on experience through construction kits. This Home edition kit consists of interlocking building blocks, one EV3 programmable brick, two large motors, one medium motor, two touch sensors, one colour sensor and one infrared sensor. The learning materials were developed by integrating Edu-robotics in selected topics of science and was used as a pedagogical tool for teaching science to sixth grade students. LEGO Mindstorms EV3 robotic kits are materials which allow students to control the behaviour of physical models using specific programming languages and involving them actively in authentic problem-solving activities.

There are many difficulties in integrating robotics activities in school curriculum. Robotics projects require constructivist methodologies, openness to novelty, encouragement of creativity and flexible school curriculum, qualities which are often missing in the current school systems. The learning materials developed by using ER provides students to experience their own creation where they construct robotics with their imagination and creative ideas. It supports the constructivist learning environment in class and make learning joyful and interesting which motivate students to create something new and empower them with the feeling of belongingness to their construction.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In recent times, the use of robotics in education has increased and there have been many efforts made by several countries to integrate robotics in science and technology mostly in school education. The use of technology must change from leaning technology to learning with technology. This will connect students to the authentic problem-based learning enabled with robotic activities. The use of robotics is based on constructionism.

The learning material using robotics was developed around constructionist learning i.e., an educational method which is based on the constructivist learning theory [1]. The learning environment provides activities embedded in problem solving procedures which enables learners to construct a knowledge while they are involved actively in design and construction of real objects. This method focusses on the role of concrete objects

in the complex process of knowledge construction [2]. These LEGO materials contribute in providing significant means for learner to assess and modify their understanding of science concepts while working together in designing, constructing, evaluating and altering objects meaningful to them [3]. Knowledge gets constructed when learners are engaged in the development of making objects and interactive about their design. Constructionism has recognition with a lot of studies in which technology is utilized to shape a setting that accelerates 'learning by doing' and 'learning by design'. Constructionism imparts association with other constructivist theories such as cognitive flexibility theory [4] and conventional knowledge [5]. However, constructionism is distinctive in that it specifies "learning by creation" as the critical features of the learning activity and "objects to think with" [6].

Educational robotics is the method during which students assemble and program robots to perform the certain behaviour for educational purposes. Therefore, educational robotics from a pedagogical perspective is considered to be grounded in the theories of classic constructivism [1] and specifically in constructionism [6]. The learning environment provides activities embedded in problem solving procedures and thus learners build an adequate knowledge as they are involved actively in the design and construction of real objects that have to mean for them in a more natural way. It allows students to express themselves freely and promotes the development of creativity and imagination as it invites students to envision what they will make and what goal they want to achieve through the programming of their constructions [7].

The challenges of incorporating technology in education are that on the one hand, teachers are not well-prepared to understand the possibilities of new technologies. On the other hand, teachers have issues regarding the developmental suitability of introducing technology and engineering in the start of grades. Most teachers are trained to a Piagetian idea of developmental stages that advises that children start the concrete operational stage at the age of six or seven. Therefore, according to Piaget, only at this age, a child obtains the capability to perform mental processes and also to modify those operations. As a consequence, a concrete operational child has a more complicated understanding of number, can imagine the world from views other than his or her own, can systematically analyse, sort, and classify objects, and can explain notions of time and causality [1].

In the initial work at MIT media lab, researchers started the development of LEGO/Logo [8]. They combined LEGO Technic products with the Logo programming language that empowered children to construct and program robots. This learning by doing method has achieved much attention in recent years. According to our idea, robotics-based learning using problem-based activities can not only increase the development of significant cognitive and metacognitive skills and abilities but can also be a vital factor for developing critical thinking in today's young learners.

Higher-order thinking, like critical thinking, decision making, creative thinking and problem solving are part of 21st century skills required in today's society [9]. Critical thinking is "the processes of analyzing and assessing thinking with an objective of improving it" [10]. Critical thinking comprises interpretation, analysis, evaluation, inference, explanation and self-regulation in their everyday lives regarding their relationships with others and the environment [9]. More precisely, critical thinking is a constructivist analysis process which stresses students to inspect what is going on in their direct and indirect environment [9], which is also known as situational awareness.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Educational utilization of educational robotics for elementary students has been around for over ten years. Educational Robotics has been presented as a powerful, flexible teaching/learning tool motivating learners to control the behaviour of physical models using specific programming languages (graphical or textual) and involving them actively in authentic problem-solving activities. It is necessary to start projects which include training of teachers on how to use educational robotics in the classroom. It is the necessity of the hour that teachers should take actions in proposing new technological tools in their classroom. Using robots as an educational tool to teach children was initiated in the early 1980's where learning is achieved most effectively by constructing robotic artefacts. Children can study through the process of designing, building and programming their robots.

Several theoretical studies and empirical research have shown that playing with robots lets students of diverse ages to develop their problem-solving capabilities. Problem solving is a demanding process which invites the students to deal with logic, semantics and sometimes with abstract thinking to conceive and solve the problem [11]. By solving authentic problems students are dynamically involved and support their exploratory attitude having incentives to study science and technology. The development of research interest is advanced and children are enabled to act like scientists and discover their original ideas and solutions thus enhancing their self-efficacy [12].

Robotics activities are generally not common in regular K–12 classrooms. One of the reasons might be that there is insufficient experimental evidence to validate the impact of robotics activities on curricular goals. Most of the literature on the robotics application in education is subjective and descriptive in quality [13], [14]. Some exploratory studies have specified positive views of the educational benefit of robotics activities among teachers and students [15], [16]. This is inspiring, but the measurable evidence is needed to convince educators of the positive effect of robotics activities on curriculum.

Some studies contributed in developing dynamic curricula that they can become the basis for the use of educational robotics in the such as TangibleK and KIBO robotics [17], [18], [19], [20]. These curricula can provide prospects for children to understand science with the help of technology and engage in engineering processes. The application of robotics, through a curriculum, offers a more efficient and planned learning environment for both children and teachers. Within this curriculum, delivering daily life related problems can improve the building of the connection between content and real life, around children [21], [22], [23]. In this method, children will be able to construct their own knowledge by using interdisciplinary skills and understanding, because they can make connections between real life and content. Therefore, implementing robotics into an educational setting needs support of stakeholders, so that children are able to understand the technology available around themselves and how it is operated. Edu-robotics could develop students' knowledge and interests in science and engineering [24]. But a majority of researchers trusted on nonexperimental methods, applied a different approach to validating their studies. However, this shows that experimental methods are greatly deficient; quantitative analysis is needed [25]. Therefore, in this study, the researcher intends to develop educational robotics integrated learning materials, designed and developed for elementary school students and was examined for its effectiveness on critical thinking skills of students in science.

IV. PURPOSE AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The theoretical framework that guides this research is founded in learning materials using was developed around the Papert's (1980) constructionist learning which is based on the constructivist theory [1]. This study looked for quantitative data that describes how constructionism-based learning materials affected elementary school student's understanding of science concepts.

The main purpose of this research was to determine the effectiveness of learning materials based on ER during Science class in school environment on critical thinking skills in Science for elementary school student around eleven to twelve age. This study compares the critical thinking skills of students who participated in the robotic intervention with those who did not participate in the intervention.

Specifically, the following research question was created:

What is the impact of robotics intervention in promoting critical thinking skill of student during science class?

V. RESEARCH DESIGN

Non-equivalent Control Group design was used for the present study. This design is very much like the pretest-posttest control group design but only difference is that it involves random assignment of intact groups to treatments, not random assignment of individuals. The design starts with natural setting of the intact classrooms assigned randomly to experimental and control group. Both the groups should be as equivalent as possible [26]. This design was found to be suitable in the present study to see the effect of learning materials developed using Educational Robotics on critical thinking skills in the natural setting without causing any disturbance to the classroom environment by either controlling or manipulating variables. The details of the design are given in figure 1:

Figure 1: Pretestposttest non-equivalent control group design

The elementary school students studying in standard VI in India constituted the population for the present study. Purposive sampling technique was implemented to select the sample for present study which is a form of non-probability sampling technique. It is characterized by the use of judgement and a deliberate effort to obtain representative samples by including presumably typical groups in the sample [26]. Schools were selected on the basis of feasibility aspect of the experimentation, data collection and with the intention of getting all the facilities required. Most importantly, the researcher had selected the schools where students had no exposure to Educational Robotics in any form of academic, co-curricular or extra-curricular activities. This was to ensure the desired outcomes of the study were not affected. However, for selecting the sample it was important for the research participants to have basic knowledge of the computers and its application. This research was intended to provide the students with completely new intervention for learning. The two schools selected for the study was affiliated to CBSE (Central Board of Secondary Education) and both the schools were situated in Pune city within 5 km distance. These two schools were taken as experimental and control group. The intact classes of VI standard had been taken as randomization was not possible because it would have affected the class schedules. The two intact classrooms of standard VI were selected for the experimentation. There were 40 students in the experimental group and 37 students in the control group initially for the study. But one student in experimental group could not attend the pre-test who was eliminated from the data. Hence the sample of the study was reduced to 39 students in experimental group and 37 students in control group. Required permissions have been taken from institution and the parents of the students before conducting the study.

V. PROCEDURE

The learning materials were developed on the lines of learning objectives as stated by NCERT (National Council for Educational Research and Training) for Grade 6 science curriculum. The materials were based on the selected topics of science in which ER can easily be integrated. The selected topics were motion, measurement of distances, electricity, light and fun with magnets. The learning materials were comprised of 5 modules and 60 lesson plans.

The designed activities were carried out in groups consisted of five or six students. When the construction of robots was completed then, the programming of robots began. In the programming phase, each student group programmed their robots, which they designed using their laptops as per the instructions given by researcher. Figure 3 shows a TriBot, one of the robots built by the students during the course. At the beginning of the intervention, the researcher gave a brief introduction about LEGO Mindstorms EV3 kits and all its parts to the students. The teacher presented a problem by asking how to design a robot which can move from one point to a different point in a straight line and asked the students to come with their ideas. Each group constructed and programmed a robot. Step wise instruction of constructing robots has been given to each group and also, they have been provided with the programming steps. Figure 4 shows the students are programming for their robots.

The experimental group participated in the intervention during their Science class for 14 weeks. The assessment instrument was 21-item critical thinking test in science with four alternatives in which there is only one right answer and rest three are distractors created by researcher. Each assessment question was derived from the Grade 6 Science curriculum.

Figure 3: A TriBot made by students

Figure 4: Students are programming their robots

VI. INSTRUMENT

The test is constructed on the basis of six dimensions of critical thinking given in Delphi report (1990). While constructing the items, age of the students and grade in which they are studying was kept in mind. The items were framed according to their intelligence level and syllabus as per the NCERT curriculum. The researcher consulted NCERT books, National Talent Search Examination (NTSE), national level Olympiad examination papers and various books related to the subject to get direction for constructing items of the test. The topics which were to be assessed was also kept in mind while construction of the items. The items of the test were based on the objectives of Science and the content of the science curriculum for grade 6 in NCERT and also covered the dimensions of Critical Thinking Skills as mentioned in Delphi Report i.e., interpretation, analysis, evaluation, inference, explanation and self-regulation. The topics which were taken from the science book to construct the test were motion, measurement of distances, light, fun with magnets and electricity. Only five topics were taken to construct the items of the test because researcher has integrated Educational Robotics in these topics to develop the learning packages.

Test-retest reliability was found from the data. First of all, the test was given to 230 students in five divisions of class VII with proper instructions and they were also informed about the purpose of test. After the gap of 15 days test was again conducted on the same group of students. Some students were absent and some were not available for the test therefore the scores of 221 students were taken for the calculation of reliability. The two sets of scores were correlated by using Pearson’s product moment correlation. The reliability coefficient of the test was found to be 0.82. The estimated value showed the stability of test score over time and reflected that the scores were reliable. Internal consistency reliability was also estimated for the Critical Thinking Skill Test in Science. It indicates the homogeneity of the test. The estimates are based on the relationship between items within a test and are derived from a single administration of the test. To estimate internal consistency of the test coefficient alpha [27] was used because coefficient alpha is more broadly applicable and become the preferred statistic for estimating internal consistency [28]. The coefficient alpha of the test was found to be 0.76.

VI. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The data were analysed using SPSS. The analysis of covariance is a statistical method for equating the two groups on one or more variables. ANCOVA was used to adjust pretest scores on dependent variable for initial differences. In this present study, the intelligence and pretest measures are statistically controlled for the experiment. The analysis of covariance corrected the initial differences in intelligence between the two groups, taking the correlation between the intelligence measures and the dependent variable outcome measures into account. It actually removes the variance due to intelligence and pretest difference from the dependent variable measures before the test of significance is applied.

To determine the overall effect of the intervention, posttest scores of control and experimental group were compared. Raven’s progressive Intelligence test has also been applied on both the groups. The scores of intelligence test were used as covariates. From the statistical point of view ANCOVA is a robust test for detecting minor variance between the means. This approach of data analysis is used to increase statistical power by reducing error variance. The mean scores of post-tests on Critical Thinking Skill Test (CTST) in the experimental and control group are shown in table 1:

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of experimental and control groups (Post-test)

Group of students	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Experimental group	16.59	2.136	39
Control group	14.41	3.193	37
Total	15.53	2.900	76

ANCOVA was performed on the post test scores taking pre-test scores on CTST and intelligence

Group of students	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Experimental group	16.657 ^a	.268	16.123	17.190
Control group	14.335 ^a	.275	13.787	14.882

scores as covariate as shown in Table 2:

Table 2: Analysis of Covariance on CTST of Experimental and Control group

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Post test scores of Critical thinking test						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	432.463 ^a	3	144.154	52.292	.000	.685
Intercept	21.468	1	21.468	7.788	.007	.098
Pretest	2.704	1	2.704	.981	.325	.013
Intelligence	340.578	1	340.578	123.544	.000	.632
Group	99.811	1	99.811	36.206	.000	.335
Error	198.485	72	2.757			
Total	18952.000	76				
Corrected Total	630.947	75				

a. R Squared = .685 (Adjusted R Squared = .672)

Table 3: Post-test scores of Critical thinking skill test

a. Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: Pre-test scores of Critical Thinking test = 6.43, Scores on Raven's Progressive Matrices = 41.26.

Table 2 reveals that the difference in the mean post test scores in CTST of the experimental group and control group is significant with $F=36.206$, $p < 0.01$ (Table 2). Hence the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in CTST of experimental and control group when pre-test on CTST and intelligence were taken as covariates is rejected and the alternative hypothesis i.e. there is a significant difference in CTST of experimental and control group when pre-test on CTST and intelligence were taken as covariates is accepted. Also it is found from Table 3 that the adjusted mean score on CTST of experimental group (mean= 16.657) is significantly higher than that of the control group (mean=14.335), indicating that the robotic intervention is effective in promoting critical thinking skill during science class in elementary school students. Bar diagram showing the pretest and posttest mean scores by group is shown in Figure 2

Figure 2: Bar Diagram of student scores on the pretest and posttest by group

VII. DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to examine the effectiveness of learning materials developed using ER on critical thinking skill in Science of elementary school students. The results of the study based on the analysis of the posttest scores of the experimental group indicate the robotics was effective at teaching science concepts like motion, measurement of distances, magnets, light and electricity. The overall difference in mean scores from the control group (M = 14.41, SD = 3.19) to the robotics intervention group ((M = 16.59, SD = 2.13) was 2.18. Moreover, there was no significant difference between the control and experimental groups pretest scores, while the robotics group had a significant increase from the pretest (M = 6.15, SD= 1.679) to the posttest (M = 16.59, SD = 2.13) F = 8.95, p < .000.

While there was a vast improvement on the posttest for the robotics group than the control group. The group performed well with robotics intervention and showed great interest and willingness to learn science concepts through robotics kits. Robotics construction gave students platform to build and design their own creativity. These learning materials are designed to make learning more visual and experiential and to allow students more flexibility in how they learn and demonstrate competence. Therefore, it can be said that the interest should be shown in developing strategies and materials to help students construct. The researchers call this effort as ‘constructional design’ [29]. It involves the design of new tools and activities to support students in their own design activities. At the same time robotics activities are based on cooperation and interaction of individuals and groups, promoting thinking through conflicts in cognitive and social level as students are required to explain ideas, opinions and thoughts and justify their answers. Additionally, students need to analyse, plan and implement their work which constitute high level mental skills. Such activities with younger ages pose some rate of failure. According to Piaget, they are in the concrete operational stage and are just moving into formal operational stage (11, 12 years old). However, dealing with problems for their level which require concrete thinking help students familiarise and deal with abstract concepts (e.g., speed, time, variable) which helps to prepare for next cognitive stage. Robotics contributes in learning programming and helps students familiarize with the basic principles of programming[30]. Programming robotic constructions creates a completely new learning environment which is highly motivating and favours the test-error strategy. Furthermore, it supports critical thinking since students need to think on the way they thought and acted[31].

The implications of the findings of this research are significant, as they provide vigorous support for the integration of robotic strategies in the curriculum of elementary education. In essence, robotics can be used as an educational technology aid to transform and improve the traditional elementary curriculum so that children can be taught about critical thinking skills which are needed in the 21st century[32]. In addition, these findings confirm that robotics can be used to teach young students about science concepts which is important for elementary education. Through integrated robotics learning materials, the student’s skills on STEM would be enhanced

[33]. Open educational robotic construct kits made students learn about the construction and execution of a robot and through this the students acquire how to solve complex problems and think logically [34].

VIII. CONCLUSION

Overall, the findings of this study support the use of educational robotics to teach science concepts in school curriculum. More research is required to validate the effectiveness of the robotics program with different populations. Educational robotics combines game with learning and thus learning becomes a fun activity that is easier, more interesting and is achieved more efficiently. The aspect of game that robotic constructions involve is important and positive factor of individual action and motivation. In conclusion, the use of robotic constructions has a lot to offer as it has already been mentioned above and to positively contribute to the increase of student's motivation, their engagement in learning, their critical thinking and their positive attitude toward education. Thus, the importance of using robots as tools for both the introduction to the robotics field as well as teaching science concepts is indisputable. There are several issues that are still open in the research and practice of educational robotics and one among them is the difficulties in incorporating robotic activities in school curricula. Much more research is needed in incorporating robotics activities in school subjects.

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